

Real-Time Object Detection and Person Recognition for Impaired Individuals Using YOLOv8 and CNN"

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Abstract — Good vision is a precious gift but unfortunately loss of vision is becoming common now a days. To help the blind people the visual world has to be transformed into the audio world with the potential to inform them about objects as well as their spatial locations. Objects detected from the scene are represented by their names and converted to speech. Everybody deserves to live independently, especially those who disabled, with the last decades, technology gives attention to disabled to make them control their life as possible. In this work, assistive system for blind is suggested, to let him knows what is around him, by using YOLO v8 for detecting objects within images quickly based on deep neural network to make accurate detection, and Open CV under Python. The obtained results indicated the success of the proposed model in giving blind users the capability to move around in unfamiliar indoor outdoor environment, through a user. This project involved Artificial intelligence to detect and analyze objects and send details via speaker In the proposed work, we solve the existing system problem by using dark net YOLO techniques that are used to reduce the recognize time of multi objects in less time with best time complexities.

Keywords—Visually Impaired, Object Detection, YOLO V8, CNN, Assistive System , Computer Vision,Image Recognition,Audio Output

individuals by providing them with real-time information about their surroundings[8]. This system comprises a walking stick and Android-based applications (APPs). The walking stick is embedded with Raspberry Pi and programmable interface controller (PIC) as a control kernel, sensors, a global position system (GPS) module, and alert-providing components. Sensors help to detect obstacles, and the VCP is informed through vibrations or a buzzer according to the obstacle detected. The GPS module receives the coordinates of the VCP's location, and the location can be tracked by parents using an APP. Another important APP is used, called an emergency APP, by which the VCP can communicate with parents or friends immediately by just shaking his/her cell phone or pushing the power button four times in 5 s in panic situations. [9]. The conversion to audio signals is done by using an e-Speak tool which forms Google's Text to Speech (GTTS) system. The prototype consists of several modules. The Raspberry Pi camera module takes the image and transfers it to the Raspberry Pi desktop[10]. The system then conveys the identified object information through a synthesized voice output, thereby enhancing visual perception and providing an immersive experience. The face motion recognition module promotes improved social interaction, while object identification increases environmental awareness.[11]. To improve the ability to detect and differentiate between different sized obstacles in outdoor environments, we introduce the Feature Weighting Block (FWB), which improves feature importance discrimination. To address the challenges of detecting cluttered outdoor environments and handling occlusions, we introduce the Adaptive Bottleneck Block (ABB), which captures varying features across different scenes. To solve the problem of detecting relatively small obstacles in outdoor environments, we propose the Enhanced Feature Attention Head (EFAH) [12]. The incorporation of attention mechanisms refines feature extraction from complex scenes, enabling the model to focus on relevant regions within images. Using the integration of Transformer architecture, the model leverages long-range dependencies and global context, leading to more accurate bounding box predictions [13]. By using CNNs (Convolution Neural Network), a widely-used approach in deep learning models, our system achieves over 95% accuracy in object detection based on camera images. Identified objects are conveyed through voice messages, making it a valuable prototype for assisting the visually impaired.[14]. In addition to that, voice guidance technique is mentioned as a way of informing individuals with sight problems where objects are located. You Only Look Once (YOLO) algorithm is employed in an object recognition deep learning model and text-to-speech (TTS) is used to synthesize a voice announcement making it convenient for blind individuals to acquire information about objects. Consequently, it presents an effective object detecting system which aids the blind in finding things within a confined area without assistance from others; and the performance of this system has been verified through experiments[15]. Most YOLO models are optimized for RGB images, which creates some limitations. While RGB images are

super sensitive to lighting conditions, infrared (IR) images using thermal data can detect objects consistently, even in low-light settings. However, infrared images present unique challenges like low resolution, tiny object sizes, and high amounts of noise, which makes direct application tricky in regard to the current YOLO models available. This situation requires the development of object detection models designed specifically for thermal images, especially for real-time recognition[16]. The same technology assists visually impaired people in their everyday activities. Considering how closely object identification relates to video analysis and visual comprehension, it has received a lot of study interest lately. The foundation of conventional object identification techniques is shallow trainable structures and handmade features. Building intricate ensembles incorporating several low-level picture characteristics with high-level context from object detectors and scene classifiers may stabilize their performance[17]. The primary objective of the research is to enhance the accuracy, precision, and recall rates in lung cancer detection, while reducing false positives and false negatives, through advanced machine learning techniques. In the proposed work, CNN is employed for feature extraction, enabling the model to capture the intricate patterns present in the DICOM images. YOLOv8, a cutting-edge object detection algorithm, is integrated to detect cancerous regions with high efficiency and speed. A comparative analysis is conducted with traditional machine learning classifiers such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), AdaBoost, Random Forest, and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), demonstrating the superior performance of the proposed deep learning models[18]. Visually impaired individuals face challenges in navigating their surroundings and identifying objects. This paper proposes an object detection system using You Only Look Once (YOLO) and the COCO dataset, combined with voice feedback, to assist blind and visually impaired people. The system utilizes a pre-trained YOLO model to detect objects in real-time video streams. Detected objects and their locations are then converted into natural language descriptions using a text-to-speech (TTS) engine, providing auditory feedback to the user[19]. Effective pain management is crucial for patient care, impacting comfort, recovery, and overall well-being. Traditional subjective pain assessment methods can be challenging, particularly in specific patient populations. This research explores an alternative approach using computer vision (CV) to detect pain through facial expressions[20]. There are two primary types of object detectors: two stage and one stage. Two-stage detectors use a complex architecture to select regions for detection, while one-stage detectors can detect all potential regions in a single shot. When evaluating the effectiveness of an object detector, both detection accuracy and inference speed are essential considerations. Two-stage detectors usually outperform one-stage detectors in terms of detection accuracy[21]. Motive of this system is to develop a solution that detects the objects present using camera, as the input device in real time and communicate [22].

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Blind people object detection is a significant problem in computer vision, as traditional object detection models often struggle to identify objects with limited size and resolution. This issue arises due to the inability of standard models, like YOLOv5, to effectively capture fine details and subtle features of small objects. The challenge becomes more pronounced in applications such as surveillance, autonomous vehicles, and medical imaging, where accurate detection of small objects is crucial. Addressing this problem requires refining the model's architecture, adjusting anchor boxes, increasing image resolution, and employing advanced loss functions to enhance the model's sensitivity to object features. Impaired individuals often struggle with detecting obstacles in their immediate environment, which can pose safety risks. Current technologies may not provide real-time, accurate detection or might lack contextual understanding. Existing models for object detection and person identification may not work well in all real-world conditions, such as crowded or dynamic environments. Achieving a balance between accuracy, speed, and resource constraints is a significant challenge.

further refine these capabilities, providing both high accuracy and real-time detection. The final system will be able to detect and classify objects in real time, providing valuable feedback to users, especially those with impairments, such as visually impaired individuals, to help them navigate their environment safely and effectively. This innovative system represents a significant step forward in using deep learning for assistive technology, providing both speed and reliability in real-world applications. Statistics is the study of gathering, arranging, analyzing, and interpreting data. Statistics covers all this, including data collection planning in the form of survey and experiment design. This is what statistics is. Statistical characteristic of image includes • Mean • Variance • Skewness • Standard deviation

Texture Analysis using the Gray-Level Co-Occurrence Matrix (GLCM). One statistical method of texture analysis that considers the spatial relationship between pixels is the gray-level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM), or the gray-level spatial dependence matrix.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this proposed system, real-time object detection will be achieved using a combination of AI, OpenCV, and YOLOv8 (You Only Look Once), a state-of-the-art object detection algorithm. The process begins with the acquisition of images through a camera system, which will capture frames of the environment in real time. Once the image is obtained, it undergoes pre-processing, including resizing, normalization, and compression. Compression reduces the image size while maintaining key features, allowing for faster processing and efficient real-time performance. Next, the system uses various daily-use objects' images to train the YOLOv8 model by performing feature extraction, which helps to identify the essential patterns in the image. This step captures object characteristics such as shapes, textures, and edges. Following feature extraction, feature fusion and dimension reduction techniques are applied to compress the image data, making it suitable for real-time object detection while maintaining sufficient accuracy. The YOLOv8 dataset, which contains labeled images of various objects, is then used to train the classifier. The performance of several classifiers is compared, and the optimal classifier is selected based on metrics such as accuracy and speed. Once the model is trained, it can classify any test image into one of the classes that it was trained to recognize. The primary YOLO, originally created by Joseph Redmon and Ali Farhadi in 2016, revolutionized the field of object detection by overcoming the limitations of traditional region proposal networks, offering a faster and more efficient design. The improvements in YOLOv8

Fig 2: YOLO v8 (You only look once v8) and CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) architecture

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the proposed system involves several key steps to achieve real-time object detection using AI, OpenCV, and YOLOv8. First, we acquire images from a live camera feed, which can be a webcam or smartphone camera, using OpenCV to capture the frames. These images are then pre-processed by resizing them to the required dimensions (e.g., 416x416), normalizing the pixel values to a range of 0-1, and applying compression techniques such as dimension reduction (using PCA or autoencoders) to ensure efficient image processing while retaining important features. The system is trained on a custom dataset consisting of daily-use objects, where feature extraction is done using convolutional layers in the YOLOv8 architecture to identify patterns and object characteristics. Feature fusion techniques are then applied to combine relevant features from various layers of the model, and dimension reduction is used to compress the data for improved real-time performance. The YOLOv8 model is trained on this dataset using a loss function that combines classification and localization errors, resulting in the model learning both object identity and position. Once the training phase is complete, we evaluate the model's performance by comparing it against other classifiers like Faster R-CNN or SSD to select the optimal one. After selecting the best-performing model, it is used to classify new test images, where the model detects and classifies objects based on its learned knowledge, outputting bounding boxes and class labels for each detected object in real-time. The system's efficiency is ensured by minimizing the computational overhead and optimizing YOLOv8's architecture for high-speed inference on available hardware, providing a reliable and robust solution for real-time object recognition.

a. Image Acquisition

Image acquisition occurs in real-time using a camera. This means that the system continuously captures images as they become available, allowing for immediate processing and analysis. Real-time image acquisition is crucial for applications where timely detection and response are essential, such as surveillance, autonomous vehicles, and interactive systems. By leveraging a camera to capture images instantly, the system can quickly detect and recognize objects, enabling rapid decision-making and action based on the processed information.

b. Pre-processing and Compression

Upon image acquisition, the system initiates pre-processing and compression to enhance efficiency in subsequent processing stages. This entails resizing, normalization, and employing compression techniques to minimize computational load and storage needs. In image dimensions, aiding pixel values, enhancing model robustness across varying lighting conditions. Compression techniques reduce image size without significant loss of information, optimizing resource utilization. These

preparatory steps streamline subsequent processing, ensuring swift and effective object detection and recognition.

c. Feature Extraction and Fusion

Feature extraction involves identifying and capturing relevant patterns or characteristics from raw data, such as images. In the context of object detection, features could include edges, textures, or colors that help distinguish between different objects. Feature fusion combines multiple types of extracted features to create a more comprehensive representation of the data, enhancing the model's ability to recognize objects accurately. By extracting and fusing features, the system can effectively distinguish between various objects in images, improving overall detection performance.

Fig 3: Bounding Boxes

d. Training Data Preparation

In the training data preparation stage, a diverse collection of images depicting everyday objects is gathered to train the model effectively. These images undergo preprocessing and feature extraction to isolate essential patterns and characteristics that distinguish one object from another. By extracting relevant features from the training images, the model learns to recognize common object attributes, enabling accurate identification during real-time object detection tasks. This meticulous preparation ensures that the model can generalize well to various objects and scenarios encountered in practical applications.

e. Training the Classifier

During the training of the classifier, the YOLO dataset is utilized alongside pre-processed and compressed features. Different classifiers are assessed for their performance using evaluation metrics, enabling the selection of the most effective one. By comparing various classifiers, the system identifies the optimal algorithm for accurately recognizing objects in real-time. This rigorous evaluation ensures that the chosen classifier can reliably classify objects with high accuracy, enhancing the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the object recognition system.

f. Real-time Object Detection

During real-time object detection, the system captures the initial frame of the video stream and promptly processes it using OpenCV and YOLO v3. Through YOLO v3's efficient object detection capabilities, the system swiftly identifies objects within the frame. Bounding boxes, accompanied by class names, are then superimposed onto the image to visually indicate the presence and type of detected objects. This real-time detection process enables rapid and accurate identification of objects, facilitating timely decision-making and response in various applications such as surveillance, robotics, and augmented reality.

g. Voice Output

In the voice output stage, upon detecting objects, a brief description or explanation of the identified objects is synthesized using text-to-speech technology like eSpeak. This process converts the textual information about the detected objects into audible speech, providing users with real-time auditory feedback. By delivering concise descriptions through voice output, the system enhances accessibility and user experience, allowing individuals to receive immediate information about detected objects without requiring visual inspection of the results.

VI.RESULT

The result of this proposed system is the successful detection and classification of objects in real-time using the trained YOLOv8 model. Upon feeding a test image into the system, the model identifies and classifies objects into predefined categories based on its training with various daily-use objects. The system outputs bounding boxes around detected objects along with their associated class labels, indicating the object's type (e.g., "chair," "table," "bottle," etc.). The confidence score for each detected object reflects the accuracy of the classification, with higher scores indicating more reliable detections. The model's ability to recognize multiple objects simultaneously and accurately classify them demonstrates the effectiveness of the YOLOv8 architecture combined with pre-processing techniques such as feature extraction, dimension reduction, and feature fusion. Performance metrics like accuracy, precision, and recall are evaluated, with the YOLOv8 model typically providing high accuracy and low latency, making it suitable for real-time applications. The comparison of various classifiers highlights YOLOv8's superior speed and efficiency in real-time object detection, solidifying it as the optimal choice for this application. This system, therefore, not only meets the requirements of real-time object recognition but also provides robust performance, essential for assisting impaired individuals by helping them navigate their environments safely and interact effectively with their surroundings.

Fig 4: Implementation Process

Fig 5: Object Detection And Text Convert Into Audio

Fig 6: Object Detection And Text Convert Into Audio

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this proposed solution that uses YOLOv8 object detection model can assist blind people with object identification in a more realistic way. The concept of how it would work involves having blind person wearing a camera and a speaker around their neck that provides audio feedback to the user. The camera will take images in real-time then input the images to the YOLOv8 model and identify the objects seen in that image. When the object is detected by the YOLOv8 model then the system will announce to the user the object's label using text-to-speech. This proposed system will help blind people overcome the major hurdle of identifying objects in their immediate environment. It is a simple yet effective solution to assist with object detection which can also help blind people improve their quality of life by using more of an autonomous style. The proposed system is a wearable device which has many applications and also helps to add more users more easily. For example, we could add additional functionalities in the proposed system for notion, such as, facial detection, identifying the color of an object, and depth perception. Again, these would help blind people with adding additional enablement for identifying objects in their environment, as well assist with their own independent enablement. Overall the proposed solution using YOLOv8 object detection model is an effective solution for helping blind people. some frames with different conditions. This project presents a novel navigation device for the visually impaired groups to help them reach the destination safely and efficiently. When it detected it alert the visually impaired people through the buzzer.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] A Review on Object Detection with Voice Support for the Visually Impaired People, G Krishna Reddy, K. Aasha Madhuri, L. Jhansi Aakanksha, P. Lahari, S. Mithila, 2024
- [2] Sundararajan, V., & Ma, S. (2024). "Real-Time Object Detection for Visually Impaired Individuals Using Smart Wearables." *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, 32(1), 45-56.
- [3] MagicEye: An Intelligent Wearable Towards Independent Living of Visually Impaired (Sethuraman et al., 2023)
- [4] "A Wearable Assistive System for the Visually Impaired Using Object Recognition and Tactile Feedback", J. Smith, A. Johnson, October 2023, *Journal of Assistive Technologies*, 10(4), 345-360
- [5] "A Wearable Assistive Device for Blind Pedestrians Using Real-Time Object Detection with a Deep Learning Approach", Y. Lee, S. Kim, J. Park, H. Cho, June 2023, *Sensors*, 22(12), 4537
- [6] "YOLOv5 Driven Smart Glasses for Visually Impaired", A. Kumar, S. Patel, May 2023, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Applications*
- [7] "Real-Time Object Detection Aid for the Visually Impaired", Rahul Mitra, September 2022